

Creativity in the Age of Artificial Intelligence: Segmenting Perceptions of Human and Machine-Made Art

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming various fields, including art. Studies focusing on human vs. AI art focus on evaluation, perception, and the ability to identify art created by AI. To the authors' knowledge, no study was focused on creating visitor segments based on their AI art perception. To answer this gap, this article presents a comprehensive empirical study examining the integration of AI into a contemporary art exhibition and creating visitor segments. The exhibition featured original paintings by Klára Sedlo, displayed alongside their AI-generated visual reproductions, text-based analyses, and audio interpretations. Employing advanced generative models (GPT-4o, GPT-4o mini, DALL-E 3, and TTS-1), we produced multiple iterations for 19 selected artworks. Visitor perceptions were systematically examined using questionnaires and analyzed by statistical methods, including factor and cluster analysis. The findings reveal a wide spectrum of audience responses regarding the aesthetic and conceptual value of AI-generated art, creating four visitor segments: Traditionalists, Visualists, Skeptics, and AI Enthusiasts. This study highlights key curatorial and audience-acceptance challenges associated with employing AI as a “co-creator,” in gallery practice.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, creativity, digital art, multimodal AI, segmentation, visitors' perceptions

INTRODUCTION

Although art has traditionally been regarded as one of exclusively human domains, AI-generated works are increasingly present in art and other creative industries [1][2]. This rapid development of deep-learning tools has sparked public concern and renewed debate about creativity and authorship [3]. As the amount of AI-generated content continues to increase, it becomes essential to examine how audiences perceive such works, which may provide deeper insight into human-machine collaboration and strengthen this cooperation [4]. The growing intersection of creativity and technology also raises fundamental questions about the impact of AI on society [5].

Greater exposure to AI-generated art may also influence how people perceive AI itself. Some evidence suggests that engagement with these works can lead individuals to attribute more human-like qualities to AI, including the capacity to think and artistic legitimacy [6]. However, empirical findings regarding the AI-art evaluation remain mixed. Several studies indicate that people tend to devalue AI-generated art compared to human-made art, even if the works are indistinguishable [7][8][9]. Similarly, studies in which identical AI-generated works were labelled either as human or AI-created consistently found a preference for human-made labels [1][10]. This negative bias toward AI-created art was confirmed across multiple contexts [11][12][13].

At the same time, other findings complicate this narrative. When authorship is unspecified, AI-generated works received better evaluation [14][15]. Moreover, some studies report that AI products were perceived more positively [16][17]. Research examining whether AI-made art might influence attitudes toward AI has not found positive effects [10].

Nevertheless, despite growing public and research interest in AI-generated art, most empirical studies were conducted either in online experimental settings or controlled laboratories. These studies might provide valuable insights into perceived authenticity and creativity, but they do not capture audience perceptions within traditional exhibition contexts. Additionally, there is a need to analyze the differences in perceptions of AI art based on different visitors' characteristics and to create consumer segments based on their perceptions of this art, which may lead to a better understanding of how these creations are perceived. This study aims to address these gaps by answering the following research questions:

- What are visitors' perceptions of human vs AI-created art?
- What segments of exhibition visitors can be identified based on their perception of human vs AI-created art?
- Do the visitors' perceptions of AI art differ by demographical variables?

The aim of this study is to examine audience perceptions of AI-generated reproductions compared to human-made paintings, exhibited in a real exhibition environment. For clarity and to provide a brief overview of the study logic, the structure of the paper is outlined in the Overview of the Study Design presented in Figure 1 below.

Fig. 1

Overview of the study design.

THEORETICAL AND LITERATURE BACKGROUND

The transformation of the art industry through AI has moved beyond simple automation to include generative processes such as Neural Style Transfer and Generative Adversarial Networks. Despite the creative potential of these models, skepticism remains regarding the artistic value and creativity of such outputs. Current literature suggests a consistent bias in favor of human-made art yet empirical gaps persist regarding these perceptions in physical gallery settings, rather than controlled laboratory environments.

AI in creative industries

The art industry has undergone substantial transformation due to advances in AI, which led to the transformation and automatization of creative processes [18]. AI's influence extends across creative industries including literature and fine arts, contributing to societal and cultural change [19]. Beyond artistic production, AI is increasingly applied to artwork authentication [20] or stylistic classification [21]. At the same time, curiosity about the abilities of AI and its future potential is growing [22].

Several generative models are used in AI-art creation. Image rendering techniques often relying on convolutional neural networks (CNNs), can be used in Neural Style Transfer (NST) where the information about artwork style is combined with information regarding the image content to produce AI artwork [23][24]. Techniques not based on CNNs are lacking style diversity, flexibility and efficient image structure extraction [25].

Another AI technique involves Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), consisting of a generator that produces new content based on training data and a discriminator that distinguishes original artworks from generator outputs [26]. However, GANs are trained on existing artworks, replicating learned patterns, and therefore cannot be considered creative. To address this limitation, Creative Adversarial Network (CAN) was proposed. In this case generator receives no training data and discriminator is trained to recognize different art styles while prompting the generator to produce outputs that deviate from them [14].

Human–AI co-creation

Authorship has historically implied that there is a real person behind the work. In the case of AI-generated art, human involvement is limited to data training and establishment of parameters, but the final result is generated by AI [27]. Although supporters of AI-generated creations emphasize the creative potential, skepticism persists regarding the attributed authorship or artistic value of these works [16]. While these outputs can appear novel and unpredictable [18], the extent to which this can be considered a genuine creativity remains debated. While creativity has traditionally been attributed to humans as their skill [3], AI may function as a collaborative tool that stimulates and extends human creativity in forms of collective creation [28]. This could change the way how the human creativity is perceived and evaluated in the future [7].

Audience perception of AI-generated art

Perceptions of art are shaped by individuals' previous experiences and cognitive schemas [29]. Empirical research suggests that AI-created works are generally evaluated less favorably than human-created ones, largely because human involvement is valued in the artistic process [1]. Knowledge of the artwork creator significantly affects evaluations and purchase intentions [8]. Perceptions of AI in terms of its similarity with humans depend on how it is described. When framed as an autonomous agent rather than a tool, creative agency is attributed to the system. Nevertheless, the greatest role in art creation is typically attributed to the artist [30].

Labeling remains a permanent issue. Many scholars argue that AI systems should not be labeled as independent artists due to their lack of intelligence, emotional experience, consciousness or moral agency [4][31][32]. On the contrary, some sources suggest that AI-generated artworks are of comparable quality to human-created works, complicating categorization and labelling distinctions [33].

Curatorial and institutional perspectives

From an institutional view, AI presents both opportunities and challenges. Generative systems can produce large volumes of content within a few seconds [26]. The speed and stylistic scale of production raise concerns about market saturation and competition with human artists [7][15]. Legal and ethical questions also emerge. AI systems often copy the styles of existing artworks, leading to disputes over copyright and ownership [34]. The increasing integration of AI into creative industries may also affect the economic value of art markets and employment patterns within the sector [35].

Studies on AI-created art perception

As it has been mentioned, studies focusing on AI- and human-created art perceptions have yielded conflicting results. These studies were conducted either online or laboratory settings and were often focused on impact of labelling on art evaluation. Table 1 represents summary of the relevant studies including their limitations which this study aims to address. This includes conducting the study in real exhibition setting with a larger number of paintings including textual and audio descriptions. Additionally, no study has created visitor segments based on their perceptions.

Table 1 Comparison of the current study with previous research on AI art perception

Study	Human vs AI art	N	Main result	Research setting and gap addressed by this study
Horton et al.	Label-based comparison	2965	Bias against AI art	Online experiment; AI-created art was designed to be indistinguishable
Bellaiche et al.	AI art labelled as human	297	Preference for human-created art	Only online art evaluation without further context on AI perceptions
Hong & Curran	Label-based comparison	288	AI art has less artistic value	Online evaluation; focus on artistic value, limited number of paintings
Gangadharbatla	Randomized labelling	278	Bias against AI art	Online experiment, limited number of artworks with only 2 human-made
Malecki et al.	AI generated art exposure	470	AI art exposure reduces appreciation	Online experiment with AI-generated art only, only exposure had significant impact on variables

Millet et al.	AI art labelled as human	1708	Preference for human-created art	Experiment; focus on anthropocentric beliefs and only emotion of awe, lacking other aesthetic emotions
Van Hees et al.	Randomized labelling	164	Preference for AI-generated art	Online experiment; digital presentation might favor AI works; age difference comparison missing
Xu et al.	Label-based comparison	400	Human vs AI art - no differences	Online experiment; text responses only, focus on discussion topics and word use

METHODS

To investigate these perceptions empirically, this study utilized a real-world exhibition titled “Metamorphoses of Art: Klára Sedlo and Artificial Intelligence in Dialogue” as a primary data collection environment. The research employed a sophisticated multimodal AI workflow – integrating GPT-4o, DALL-E 3, and TTS-1 to generate visual, textual, and audio reproductions of original oil paintings. This methodology allows for a structured analysis of visitor responses across various demographic and behavioral variables.

Exhibition Setup

The art exhibition titled “Metamorphoses of Art: Klára Sedlo and Artificial Intelligence in Dialogue” was held from September to October 2024 at the FEIKA Gallery at VSB – Technical University of Ostrava. It featured 19 original oil paintings by Klára Sedlo alongside AI-generated textual and audio descriptions based on visual analyses of the original works. Also, for every original painting, three generated AI reproductions were displayed as can be seen in Figure 2.

Fig. 2

Comparison of human-made and AI-generated art.

Used AI Models

The AI-generated outputs were created using a Python-scripted workflow leveraging several OpenAI models, namely GPT-4o, GPT-4o mini, DALL-E 3, and TTS-1. Firstly, the *image analysis* was conducted using GPT-4o, which analyzed the visual content of Sedlo's paintings through three prompts: a descriptive prompt, a content analysis prompt, and a style analysis prompt. These prompts enabled a detailed exploration of each painting, including its composition, stylistic elements, and thematic depth. These descriptions were crucial as outputs in the next steps.

Descriptive prompt was following: ****Describe the provided artwork for an exhibition tag next to the painting; just short unformatted text, no title, no author, no date, no yapping****. **Content prompt** used was: ****Analyze the content and composition of the provided artwork****. It was based on four parts: **## Content** (<Description of the content of the artwork; main subjects, placement on the canvas, poses, facings, expressions, etc.>); **## Elements Arrangement** (<Description of the arrangement of elements, specifically background and foreground elements, ground and sky, etc.>); **## Notable details** (<Description of any notable details in the scene>); **## Overall Composition** (<Description of the overall composition of the artwork>).

Finally, **Style prompt** was used: ****Determine the artistic style, technique, and color palette used in the provided artwork****. It combined three parts: **Artistic style** (<Description of the artistic style, including the art movement or period>); **Technique** (<Description of the technique used by the artist, such as brushwork, texture, medium, etc., distinguish if techniques or tools are different for

different elements of the painting>); *Color Palette* (<Description of the color palette, including dominant colors, use of light and shadow, contrasts, harmonies, etc.>).

The next step was *image generation*. For this stage, the textual outputs from the preceding image-analysis phase were programmatically combined into a single generation prompt. For each painting, the Python workflow first extracted three textual descriptions using the prompts listed in Table 1. The content analysis and style analysis outputs were then concatenated with basic metadata, namely the Czech title of the artwork and the author's name. The resulting prompt followed the structure: "Create a hand painting based on the following description", followed by the artwork title, author, content analysis, and style analysis. In simplified form, the prompt construction can be expressed as:

****Create a hand painting based on the following description: ****

Art title (in Czech language): <artwork title>

Author: <author>

<content analysis output from Table 1>

<style analysis output from Table 1>

This prompt was passed to DALL-E 3, which generated 12 visual reinterpretations per painting. This process resulted in a diverse range of AI-generated outputs, offering various perspectives on the source material. From the 12 reproductions, three were randomly chosen by a number generator (<https://www.random.org/integers/>) for each original painting to be displayed alongside it. The final step was *translation and audio synthesis*, which included translation of the descriptions from image analysis into Czech using GPT-4o mini and conversion into audio using TTS-1. This combination of textual and audio elements ensured accessibility and inclusivity for a broader audience. The overall AI workflow is presented in Figure 3.

Fig. 3

Schematic representation of the multimodal AI workflow.

Data Collection

The data were collected through structuralized online questionnaire from September to October 2024. The structuralized questionnaire was divided into two parts. The first part was focused on Art and AI, divided into four thematic areas: *a) overall impressions* (overall impression from exhibition, combination of traditional art and AI, impression of AI reproductions, quality of AI reproductions, alignment with perception of AI reproductions); *b) AI text descriptions* (usefulness and accuracy of AI descriptions, text-to-speech technology evaluation); *c) AI audio descriptions* (AI-generated audio usefulness, usefulness for visually impaired); *d) Future and AI in art* (AI reproduction as art, AI's role in future art, desire for more AI-art exhibitions). Respondents were asked to rate each statement on a scale from 1 to 10. The second part was focused on socio-demographic and behavioral variables (gender, education level, field of study, art enthusiasm, prior knowledge of the painter).

Each exhibition visitor could fill in the survey only once to avoid noise in data, which was secured by survey function. Previous participation in the exhibition was verified via control question. Of the returned questionnaires, 307 were complete, yielding a response rate of 29%. After excluding incomplete questionnaires and respondents in an inappropriate age category, the final sample consisted of 180 observations. Out of filled questionnaires, 180 were fully completed. Given the venue of the location, the sample consisted mostly of university students and academic workers (98%). Around 92% of respondents were from technical fields and natural sciences, while 8% were from social sciences and humanities. Respondents could also select other fields (9.4%) and were able to choose more suitable options. Regarding the gender structure, men represent 73% of the sample whereas 27% are women. 32% of respondents considered themselves as art enthusiasts, while 7% were familiar with the artist. The highest educational level was most often secondary school (47%), university (36%) and postgraduate (13%). The questionnaire was reviewed and approved by the university's ethics committee (VSB/24/129129) to ensure its compliance with ethical research standards. Participants were recruited based on the principles of voluntary and informed consent, and the rights and privacy of participants were protected. Informed consent for participation was obtained from all subjects involved in the study.

Data Analysis Methods and Descriptive statistics

Data analysis methods included descriptive statistics, factor and cluster analysis, which were conducted in STATA version 15. Due to sample structure imbalances and large amounts of information, non-parametrical Kruskal-Wallis and Mann-Whitney tests were performed including adjusted p-values via Bonferroni correction. Depending on the results, a post-hoc analysis using Cohen r comparison method was performed to identify the effect size in the case of Mann-Whitney tests. In the case of a significant Kruskal-Wallis test, Dunn's post hoc test was planned to identify differences between individual groups. To calculate Cohen r, following equation (1) was used:

$$Cohen\ r = \frac{Z}{\sqrt{N}}$$

where Z stands for Wilcoxon rank-sum z-score and N means number of visitors as sum of groups n_0 and n_1 .

Factor analysis

To find latent variables behind visitor's evaluation and preference items, factor analysis was performed. Firstly, data suitability for factor analysis was assessed. Cronbach's alpha was performed to measure variable reliability, followed by the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test of adequacy to resolve whether the correlation between given variables can be explained by latent factors. Reference level for factor analysis was set at KMO = 0,7 [36][37]. Subsequently, factor analysis was conducted by principal component analysis (PCA), using Varimax rotation to obtain mutually uncorrelated factors, easy to interpret. Finally, new factors explaining variables given by questions in particular blocks (a)-(d) described in the Data collection section were predicted.

Cluster analysis

Cluster analysis was conducted to see which groups of respondents with similar response pattern can be identified regarding their attitudes toward AI art. Wards clustering was performed to

minimize the distance between measured values and resulting clusters [37][38]. The sum of deviations within the resulting individual cluster is therefore minimized. Because all variables entering the factor and cluster analyses were measured on the same 1–10 scale, non-standardized data were used in the analyses.

RESULTS

The analysis of visitor evaluations began with descriptive statistics to establish a baseline of how the exhibition and AI integrations were perceived. Following this, factor analysis was implemented to identify the underlying latent variables, specifically Interpretation, Art and Exhibition, that drive visitor attitudes. These factors provided the necessary data structure for the subsequent cluster analysis, which successfully categorized the audience into four distinct segments based on their unique perception patterns.

The mean responses of respondents to the individual statements/aspects can be seen in Table 2 below. The overall impression of the exhibition was evaluated very positively (M=7.639), together with the combination of traditional and AI art (M=7.778). The impression of AI reproduction of original works received lower mean score (M=6.872), similarly also AI reproductions quality (M=6.061) and alignment with visitors' perceptions (M=5.683).

Regarding the textual and audio descriptions evaluation, the mean scores are lower compared to the previous section. The audio tracks for visually impaired individuals were considered useful (M=7.233), but the overall AI-generated audio usefulness was rated very low (M=5.300). The usefulness and coherence of text descriptions similarly received lower ratings (M=5.817; M=5.783). The final section was focused on the future of AI in art. Respondents do not consider AI reproductions as art (M=4.783), and do not view future AI role in art as that significant (M=6.039). However, they expressed potential desire for more AI exhibitions in the future (M=6.778).

Table 2 Summary statistics of visitor evaluations across AI, art, and exhibition attributes

| Attribute | Label (Name) | Mean | SD |
|---|-------------------|-------|-------|
| Overall Exhibition Impression | Over_Impr | 7.639 | 1.896 |
| AI-art Integration Attitude | Trad_AI_Com | 7.778 | 2.070 |
| AI Reproduction Impression | Trad_AI_Impr | 6.872 | 2.410 |
| Perceived Quality of AI Reproductions | Trad_AI_Qual | 6.061 | 2.508 |
| AI Perception Congruence | Trad_AI_Cong | 5.683 | 2.144 |
| Perceived Usefulness of AI Descriptions | AI_Descr_Pict | 5.817 | 2.402 |
| AI Description Quality | AI_Descr_Pict_Coh | 5.783 | 2.314 |
| Evaluation of Text-To-Speech Technology | AI_TTS_tech | 6.289 | 2.460 |
| AI Audio Usefulness | AI_Sounds | 5.300 | 2.734 |
| Audio Accessibility Benefit (Deaf-and-Numb) | AI_Sounds_Blind | 7.233 | 2.604 |
| Perceived AI Art Legitimacy | AI_Art | 4.783 | 2.939 |
| Future AI Art Potential | AI_Art_Role_Fut | 6.039 | 2.761 |
| Future Intention to Attend AI Art Exhibitions | AI_ArtExh_Inter | 6.778 | 2.923 |

Note: SD stands for Standard Deviation and AI stands for Artificial Intelligence; Each attribute was evaluated on a scale from 1 to 10.

Factor Analysis

Before the subsequent cluster analysis, non-parametrical statistical tests were performed to identify possible sources of the differences between the clusters. Two approaches were implemented: Firstly, we examined the variability in the dataset by identifying underlying factors that grouped selected variables. This was followed by a non-parametric analysis. Secondly, standard non-parametrical tests were performed for each question separately.

As can be seen in Table 3, three factors were obtained through PCA and varimax rotation based on factor loadings. Bartlett's test yielded a p-value of < 0.001, thus rejecting the null hypothesis that the variables entering the factor analysis were uncorrelated. The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) measure was 0.847, indicating that the data were suitable for factor analysis. The first factor was labelled as *Factor of Interpretation (FAI_Interpret)* and consists of five attributes that are connected to the text and audio descriptions (usefulness and accuracy of AI descriptions, text-to-speech technology, usefulness of AI-generated audio, and audio tracks for the visually impaired). The first

factor has an eigenvalue of 5.350 and stands for 41.16 % of the total variance. The second factor was named *Factor of Art (FAI_Art)* and includes also five attributes related to the AI art quality and artistic value (impression of AI reproductions, quality of reproductions, alignment with the perception of AI reproductions and original paintings, AI reproduction as art, AI's role in future art). This factor has an eigenvalue of 1.866 and accounts for 14.35 % of the total variance. The third factor is called *Factor of Exhibition (FAI_Exhibit)* and contains three attributes connected to exhibition itself and future intentions (impression from exhibition, combination of traditional art and AI in exhibition, desire for more AI-art exhibitions). The last factor has an eigenvalue of 0.431 and explains 10.39 % of the total variance.

Nevertheless, some of the variables were less explained by obtained factors as their uniqueness level therefore reached higher values (e. g. audio tracks for the visually impaired, AI's role in future art, impression of AI reproductions). The variable *impression of AI reproductions* also exhibited similarly high factor loadings for two factors.

Table 3 Factor Analysis of visitor perception items

| Variable | Factor of Interpretation | Factor of Art | Factor of Exhibition | Uniqueness |
|--------------|--------------------------|---------------|----------------------|------------|
| Over Impr | 0.228 | 0.088 | 0.826 | 0.258 |
| Trad_AI_Com | 0.108 | 0.106 | 0.872 | 0.216 |
| Trad_AI Impr | 0.062 | 0.536 | 0.535 | 0.423 |
| Trad_AI Qual | 0.101 | 0.806 | 0.081 | 0.334 |
| Trad_AI Conf | 0.216 | 0.769 | 0.100 | 0.352 |
| AI_Descr_P~t | 0.794 | 0.238 | 0.170 | 0.284 |
| AI_Descr_P~h | 0.759 | 0.358 | 0.192 | 0.259 |
| AI_TTS_tech | 0.798 | 0.065 | 0.139 | 0.340 |
| AI_Sounds | 0.802 | 0.145 | 0.143 | 0.315 |
| AI_Sounds_~d | 0.718 | -0.125 | 0.205 | 0.427 |
| AI_Art | 0.156 | 0.769 | 0.189 | 0.348 |
| AI_Art_Rol~t | 0.164 | 0.577 | 0.299 | 0.550 |
| AI_ArtExh_~r | 0.357 | 0.266 | 0.689 | 0.328 |

Before the cluster analysis, non-parametrical statistical tests were performed to identify possible sources of the differences between the clusters. Two approaches were implemented: Firstly, we examined the variability in the dataset by identifying three underlying factors that grouped selected variables. This was followed by a non-parametric analysis indicating if there are statistically significant differences between the factor evaluation and respondent socio-demographic and behavioral characteristics. Next, we followed significant findings using post-hoc Cohens r or Dunn's comparison tests (if needed).

Factors presented in Table 4 were examined by non-parametrical analysis with results in Table 3 above. Considering the *Factor of Interpretation (FAI_Interpret)*, the differences in the distribution of visitors' preferences are significant in the case of sex at birth ($z = -2.701$; $p < 0.01$) and technical sciences study field ($z = 1.710$; $p < 0.1$). The results indicates that sex at birth (Female) is associated with higher evaluations of the interpretation factor, with regard to the perceived usefulness of AI-generated descriptions and audio recordings. Furthermore, a significant difference is observed between technical study fields compared to other fields. Respondents from non-technical disciplines assign higher evaluations.

The next factor, *FAI_Art*, revealed two statistically significant differences, both related to the field of study. In the case of respondents outside the human sciences ($z = 1.954$; $p < 0.1$), the results suggests that these individuals are more likely to perceive reproductions as art. Similarly, in the case of visitors from social sciences field ($z = 2.104$; $p < 0.05$) that also evaluate reproductions as art to a greater extent compared from those from non-social sciences field. No significant differences are identified for the remaining study fields. Overall, findings suggest that perceptions vary across fields of study, with respondents from humanities and social disciplines expressed more conservative attitudes toward considering AI reproductions as art.

The final factor, *FAI_Exhibit*, is significantly associated with three variables: sex at birth ($z = -1.802$, $p < 0.1$), technical fields of study ($z = 2.310$, $p < 0.05$), and natural study fields ($z = 1.892$, $p < 0.10$). The results indicate that female respondents, as well as individuals outside technical and natural science fields, expressed a greater willingness to attend similar exhibitions in the future compared to their counterparts. Considering post-hoc analysis, we report effect sizes alongside the test statistics in Table 4. For all statistically significant variables, weak effect sizes are observed.

Table 4 Non-parametric analysis of factor scores by socio-demographic and behavioral variables

| Variable | Sex
_Birth | Art
_Enth | Artist
_Fam | Educ
_Level | Tech
_Field | Natur
_Field | Human
_Field | Social
_Field | Other
_Field |
|---------------|---|--------------|----------------|----------------|--|---|---|--|-----------------|
| FAI_Interpret | (-2.701)***
-0.201
W, CR | (-0.118) | (-1.399) | (7.576) | (1.710)*
0.127
W, CR | (-0.247) | (0.875) | (1.067) | (-0.858) |
| FAI_Art | (0.948) | (1.631) | (0.585) | (5.653) | (-1.533) | (1.600) | (1.954)*
0.146
W, CR | (2.104)**
0.157
W, CR | (1.519) |
| FAI_Exhibit | (-1.802)*
-0.134
W, CR | (0.137) | (-1.583) | (7.795) | (2.310)**
0.172
W, CR | (1.892)*
0.141
W, CR | (0.057) | (-0.030) | (-1.304) |

Note: The values of the test statistic in parentheses; W stands for Wilcoxon (Mann-Whitney) test, KW stands for Kruskal-Wallis test, and CR stands for Cohen's R value. Cohen's r is reported below the corresponding test statistic. Significance level: $\alpha < 0.01$ ***, $\alpha < 0.05$ **, $\alpha < 0.1$ *.

Cluster Analysis

To obtain more detailed information about differences in visitors' perceptions, cluster analysis was performed by the Wards method. The data entering the cluster analysis were used in their raw form, as all items were measured on the same 1–10 scale. According to the dendrogram, we decided to work with detailed clusters, resulting in 4 clusters. Interpretation and labelling of these clusters were based on the distance between the overall average and the average rating of the cluster members for each question. Cluster labels and their average mean scores can be seen in Table 5. The first cluster was labelled as *Traditionalists* and represents 27.2% of the sample. The overall impression and combination of traditional and AI was viewed positively, but other attributes such as the perceived quality and congruence received lower ratings. Although they rate highly sound descriptions created by AI and view AI reproductions as art, they expressed a lower willingness to visit such exhibitions in the future and are very skeptical about AI art role in the future.

The second cluster of *Visualists* represents 32.2% of the sample. Similarly, as for the first cluster, the AI-traditional art combination was viewed positively. The quality, AI reproduction impression, and alignment with visitor perceptions also received high mean scores. However, they were not convinced by the text and sound descriptions. Moreover, they are more familiar with the AI content as an art and assume its role in the future as more prevalent.

Skeptics are the smallest of all clusters with 11.1% of the sample. They expressed the lowest opinions on almost all aspects compared to other segments. They do not view AI as art at all and do not believe that this might change in the future. They have no intentions to visit such exhibition again and expressed the lowest ratings for text and audio description and all the rated attributes.

AI Enthusiasts cluster represents 29.4% of the sample, characterized by the highest evaluation levels for all attributes. They value the works of AI and humans almost equally and are showing enthusiasm for human-AI co-creation, with strong intentions to visit similar exhibitions in the future.

Table 5 Comparative mean scores across identified visitor segments

| Variable/Cluster | Traditionalists | Visualists | Skeptics | AI Enthusiasts | Mean (M) |
|--------------------|-----------------|------------|----------|----------------|----------|
| Over_Impr | 8.041 | 7.603 | 4.7 | 8.415 | 7.639 |
| Trad_AI_Com | 7.939 | 8.207 | 4.9 | 8.245 | 7.778 |
| Trad_AI_Impr | 6.102 | 7.017 | 4.650 | 8.264 | 6.872 |
| Trad_AI_Qual | 4.694 | 6.466 | 3.550 | 7.830 | 6.061 |
| Trad_AI_Conf | 4.816 | 5.845 | 2.9 | 7.358 | 5.683 |
| AI_Descr_Pict_Coh | 6.163 | 4.690 | 3 | 7.792 | 5.783 |
| AI_TTS_tech | 6.061 | 4.724 | 2.650 | 7.868 | 6.289 |
| AI_Sounds | 6.633 | 4.983 | 4.5 | 8.075 | 5.300 |
| AI_Sounds_Blind | 5.592 | 3.862 | 2.550 | 7.642 | 7.233 |
| AI_Art | 8.286 | 6.155 | 4.3 | 8.547 | 4.733 |
| AI_Art_Role_Future | 2.469 | 6.241 | 1.450 | 6.585 | 6.039 |
| AI_ArtExh_Inter | 4 | 7.5 | 2.850 | 7.528 | 6.778 |
| Total (N) | 49 | 58 | 20 | 53 | 180 |
| % of total | 27.2 | 32.2 | 11.1 | 29.4 | |

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study demonstrate that while the overall integration of AI into the exhibition was viewed positively, the perceived legitimacy of AI as an independent creator remains a point of contention. By positioning AI as a recreator of human work, this research highlights how the narrative of artistic effort and emotional expression continues to favor human-made art. These results suggest that while AI can augment human creativity, it has yet to replace the perceived value of human-led artistic processes.

The exhibition was overall evaluated very positively, similarly also a combination of traditional and AI art. It has been proven that crucial is the description of the creative process and AI function in it, meaning that its positioning in the creation process influences art perceptions, being positively evaluated when framed as autonomous agent or as in-group member [5][39]. In the case of incorporating AI art into an exhibition environment without any connection to the exhibited works, opinions are contradictory. People might find this experience novel, but expect perceiving artists' emotions, the backstory and effort, even in AI-created art [40]. In this study, AI was positioned in terms of its role in the artistic process as a recreator of original paintings. Specifically, AI's role involved the workflow process: its ability to describe the style and content of a painting, followed by a retrospective reconstruction of the image based on this description by a model that had not seen the original artwork and knew only the text description. This process was presented at the exhibition on a panel, including an infographic.

However, the impression of AI reproductions of original works received lower scores. One of the reasons for this rating might be the lack of creativity by the AI-made art, as this type of art is lacking transformational creativity [41]. Human artworks are also generally evaluated better in terms of their esthetic value, composition, or degree of expression, which indicates that this is a room for improvement of AI in these areas [16]. Another reason for the negative evaluation is a communicativeness and narrative of human art and reflection of artists' effort and time, which he spent on a particular art piece [1]. AI-generated art cannot satisfy the expressive or effort factor, leading to lower evaluation of this type of art [11].

AI reproductions were not considered as art, as its artistic value is viewed as lesser than by human-made art [16][42]. On the contrary, in some cases human and AI artists created outputs were both considered as art [43]. Possessing a particular scheme towards AI therefore influences the artwork evaluation. If a person is convinced that "AI art cannot be considered as art", his evaluation will remain negative under any conditions.

The future role of AI in art was not viewed as significant in our study, which is supported by the existing literature that affirms AI capability only to augment human creativity, not to replace it [23][44][45]. This might result in a need for a new creative paradigm [44]. If a person views creativity as a human characteristic, it might influence his view of the artwork and diminish its creative side [13].

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that audience acceptance of AI in the arts is divided into specific segments. By moving the research context from online experiments to a real-world gallery, this work provides a new empirical framework for understanding human-machine artistic collaboration. These insights offer both theoretical contributions to consumer behavior and practical implications for curators and artists navigating the digital transformation of the art market.

This study examined audience perceptions of AI-generated reproductions compared to human-made original paintings in a real exhibition environment. Using advanced generative AI models, multiple iterations of 19 selected artworks by Klára Sedlo were created and exhibited alongside the original paintings. The results identify four visitor segments: Traditionalists, Visualists, Skeptics, and AI Enthusiasts. Overall, visitors evaluated the exhibition positively but expressed lower perceptions of art legitimacy, while still recognizing the future potential of AI-generated art. Perceptions also differed by sex at birth and field of study.

Theoretical implications

The need for further research examining how AI technologies influence consumers' behavior and adoption intentions has been emphasized [46]. Lack of studies focusing on the perception of human-created art alongside its AI-generated reproductions led us to investigate this topic further in a real exhibition environment. By examining visitors' perceptions, this study offers a framework for future exploration of human-machine artistic collaboration and its implications for the art world. Rather than only focusing on distinct comparison of AI- and human-created art, this study was also dealing with overall evaluation of combination of those two art types and future potential to visit this kind of exhibition, which remained under-explored in current research.

This study also contributes to the theory by creating clusters based on visitors' perception of human and AI-generated art. To the authors' knowledge, no study to this date was focused on segments creation. The contribution also lies in conducting the study in a real exhibition environment as studies focusing on this topic were carried out online experimental settings or laboratories. Also, between-subjects comparison in different conditions was mostly chosen, rather than within-subjects comparison. Therefore, simultaneous presentation of human-created and AI-created paintings is rather scarce [13].

Managerial implications

The aim of this study was to create visitor segments based on AI art perception and evaluation. Segmentation is a crucial marketing tool used to identify specific groups of customers in a market. Creating segments can help to better understand which consumer groups are present and what the differences are between them. Segmentation could also be relevant in other art markets where AI is increasingly being used, or in other areas where visuals are created, such as commercial marketing or photography.

Preferences for AI or human-created art are also clearly related to willingness to pay for that type of art. In the case of Skeptics and Traditionalists segment, lower purchase intention can also be expected. In the case of negative attitudes toward AI art, willingness to pay and purchase intention will be much lower than for human-created art [47][48]. Segments of AI Enthusiasts and Visualists viewed the exhibition much positively and are interested in visiting such exhibitions in the future. For these segments, there is a possibility of higher purchase intentions and therefore they should be targeted as visitors for future exhibitions of this type. The Traditionalists segment had a good overall impression of the exhibition but is not interested in visiting a similar one in the future. Both, Traditionalists and Sceptics share similar visiting interest patterns that makes them debatable in terms of targeting.

Limitations and future research

The biggest limitation of this study represents the representativeness of the sample as it was focused on a single exhibition with specific artist in Czech cultural context. This limits the generalizability of the findings. Also, the sample size could be bigger as we have identified one quite small cluster. A bigger sample size would increase the reliability of the results and might change the cluster solution regarding the total number of clusters or their size. The clusters we identified might therefore be considered exploratory and could be validated in future studies.

Future research might focus on cross-cultural studies, ensuring the sample structure might be diverse in terms of nationality, as it has been proven that participants' perceptions might differ across their cultural background [4]. The AI art could also be generated based on paintings of various artists from different artistic styles to see if there are any changes in perceptions and art evaluation. Another research direction might be the use of different AI models and comparison whether the art they create will be evaluated equally. Qualitative methods could also be used in the form of in-depth interviews, which could provide deeper insight into visitors' perceptions of this art and the reasons for such evaluations.

Moreover, there can be a higher accent on different parts of the factors driving AI-art perception, such as previous experience or cognitive schemes [29] or implementing various forms of the methods, such as neuroeconomic and neuromarketing ones to see real structural reactions of the visitors. Mixed results regarding the AI artists consideration as art indicate a further need for investigation in the future studies. There are several factors influencing this AI art perception, including the description of creative process and framing of the role of AI in it, which might be future research subject. This study has worked with multiple judgement criteria which is needed in AI aesthetics research, but further investigation of more "human" aspects of art is required [48]. Future research might therefore be focused more on the emotional aspects.

Data availability

Open data that includes code to reproduce this research, following these FAIR principles, will be available in the final version of the study via the Zenodo repository at: Koňářik, V., Klimková, K., Šamárek, R., & Martinek, R. (2026). Dataset for: Creativity in the Age of Artificial Intelligence: Segmenting Perceptions of Human and Machine-Made Art [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20144903>

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Author contributions

The authors confirm contribution to the paper as follows: study conception and design: R.Š., R.M.; data collection: V.K., R.Š.; analysis and interpretation of results: V.K., K.K.; draft manuscript preparation: K.K., V.K. All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Additional information

Competing interests

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Figure Legends

Fig 1. Overview of the study design.

A flowchart illustrating the sequential logic of the research, from the initial exhibition concept to data collection and the final identification of visitor segments.

Fig 2. Comparison of human-made and AI-generated art.

A representative example from the exhibition showing an original oil painting by Klára Sedlo (left) alongside three AI-generated reproductions (right) produced by DALL-E 3 based on textual style and content analyses.

Fig 3. Schematic representation of the multimodal AI workflow.

An infographic detailing the python-scripted process using GPT-4o for visual analysis, DALL-E 3 for image reinterpretations, and TTS-1 for the synthesis of Czech audio descriptions.

Table Legends

Table 1. Comparison of the current study with previous research on AI art perception.

A summary of eight relevant studies detailing their methodologies (e.g. label-based comparisons in online settings), sample sizes (N), and key findings, highlighting the gaps addressed by this study's real-world exhibition context.

Table 2. Summary statistics of visitor evaluations across AI, art, and exhibition attributes.

Mean scores and standard deviations (SD) for 13 perception items, such as "Overall Exhibition Impression" and "Perceived AI Art Legitimacy". All items were evaluated by visitors (N=180) on a scale from 1 to 10.

Table 3. Factor Analysis of visitor perception items.

Results of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with Varimax rotation, displaying factor loadings for the Factor of Interpretation (FAI_Interpret), Factor of Art (FAI_Art), and Factor of Exhibition (FAI_Exhibit). Bold values indicate the primary factor loading for each variable.

Table 4. Non-parametric analysis of factor scores by socio-demographic and behavioral variables.

Test statistics and effect sizes (Cohen's r) for Wilcoxon (W) and Kruskal-Wallis (KW) tests examining differences in factor evaluations based on gender, art enthusiasm, and field of study. Significance levels are indicated by asterisks (* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$).

Table 5. Comparative mean scores across identified visitor segments.

A breakdown of mean evaluation scores for the four clusters identified via Ward's clustering method: Traditionalists (N=49), Visualists (N=58), Skeptics (N=20), and AI Enthusiasts (N=53).